

DIGITAL LIBRARIES AND PERSONALISED LEARNING EXPERIENCES OF FINAL YEAR ECONOMICS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of educational tools in digital libraries on the personalized learning experiences of final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. A descriptive research design was employed, with the use of questionnaire tagged Digital Libraries and Personalized Learning Experiences of Students Questionnaire (DLPLESQ) as instrument of data collection. A total of 212 final year economics education students were selected for the study using snowball sampling technique. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to provide answers to research questions. Additionally, inferential statistics in form of regression analysis was used to test the relevant hypothesis. The findings revealed that digital library tools have a significant positive impact on students' personalized learning experiences of students ($\beta_1 = 2.002$; $P < 0.05$). The study also demonstrated that final year Economics education students are "Not Aware" of the resources in digital libraries in public universities in Lagos State Nigeria. Out of the 13 digital library resources listed, sampled students seem to be "Aware" of only three resources which are "Google Scholar", "Oxford Academic" and "Research4life". Furthermore, the study showed that final year Economics education students make use of the digital library resources "Monthly". Based on these findings, the study recommended strategies to enhance the utilization of digital libraries, such as improving access to devices and internet connectivity, providing training programs to enhance digital literacy skills, and integrating digital library resources into the economics education curriculum.

KEYWORDS: Digital libraries, economics education, personalised learning, public universities

INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

In recent years, there has been a significant shift in the way education is delivered, particularly in higher education institutions. With the rapid advancement of technology, traditional learning methods are being augmented or replaced by digital platforms and personalized learning experiences (Adakawa et al., 2021). This shift has been particularly notable in the field of education, where students are increasingly relying on digital resources to enhance their learning. Especially for students of Economics education, a course which requires access to a wide range of scholarly resources, including academic journals, research papers, economic data, and statistical analyses. Akpojotor (2016) averred that digital library tools provide students with convenient and

immediate access to these resources, enabling them to stay updated with the latest research, theories, and methodologies in the field. Moreover, digital libraries offer search functionalities that allow students to efficiently locate relevant materials, saving time and effort in their research process. In the words of Okiki and Ireko (2022), the availability of online databases and digital resources also expands the scope of students' exploration, enabling them to explore interdisciplinary connections and perspectives.

Digital library tools provide the necessary infrastructure to enhance the study of economics education, fostering a deeper understanding of economic concepts and facilitating critical analysis and research in the field. A digital library is a collection of digital objects that can include text, visual material, audio material, and video material, stored as electronic media formats, along with means for organizing, storing, and retrieving the files and media contained in the library collection (Popoola & Adedokun, 2023). Digital libraries have become increasingly important in the educational landscape. They offer students access to a wide range of digital resources, including e-books, scholarly articles, research papers, and multimedia content relevant to their field of study (Niqresh, 2019). These resources are available online, allowing students to conveniently access them from anywhere and at any time. Digital libraries often offer search features and organizational tools that facilitate efficient information retrieval and management. By utilizing these resources, students can enhance their understanding of different topics, gain exposure to contemporary research, and access supplementary materials that enrich their learning experience (Stolyarov, 2021).

Personalised learning experiences, on the other hand, focus on tailoring education to the individual needs, preferences, and pace of each student. By leveraging technology and innovative instructional approaches, personalised learning enables students to engage with content that aligns with their interests, strengths, and learning styles (Tsybulsky 2020). This approach empowers students to take ownership of their learning journey, fosters critical thinking skills, and encourages self-directed learning. A useful learning activity that supports important personalised, emotional, and cognitive learning experiences is provided by digital libraries, which further personalised learning.

While there may be studies exploring digital libraries and personalized learning experiences in general or in other disciplines, there seems to be dearth of research specifically addressing the needs and experiences of final-year Economics education students in public universities in Lagos State. On this premise, this study focuses specifically on final-year Economics education students in public universities in Lagos State and aims to examine the impact of digital libraries and personalized learning on their educational journey. In summary, this study transforms economics education: lecturers refine teaching with digital tools, students gain knowledge autonomy and skills for future success, and the study underscores learning innovation and advocates positive change in education.

The study aims to address the seemingly lack of comprehensive understanding and assessment of the role of digital libraries in facilitating personalized learning experiences for final year Economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. Despite the availability of digital resources, it remains unclear how students are utilizing digital libraries and whether these resources effectively support their individual needs, interests, and learning styles. Additionally, the extent to which personalized learning

experiences are integrated into the final year curriculum and the impact of digital library tools on students' academic performance and career readiness in the field of economics education are not well-explored. Therefore, there is a pressing need to investigate the current state of digital libraries and their potential for enhancing personalized learning experiences in order to inform educational practices, policy-making, and the future development of digital resources in public universities in Lagos State.

The objectives of this article are to:

1. Examine the level of awareness of final year economics education students of the resources in the digital library in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria
2. Assess the frequency of usage of the resources in the digital library for research purposes by final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria
3. Find out if there are any challenges faced by final year economics education students of public universities in Lagos State in accessing and navigating digital library tools.
4. Assess the influence of frequency of usage of the resources in the digital library on personalised learning experiences of final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria

Hypothesis

H₀₁: Frequency of usage of digital libraries resources does not have any significant influence on personalised learning experiences of final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explores the various scholarly works which showed the current understanding of digital libraries and their role in facilitating personalized learning experiences among final year Economics education students. By synthesizing and analysing previous studies, theories, and best practices, this literature review establishes a foundation for the research, identify research gaps, and guide the investigation into the utilisation and influence of digital library resources on the educational landscape in Lagos State's public universities.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on Technology Acceptance Model for the digital library resources and Constructivism Theory for personalised learning experiences.

Fred Davis introduced the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in 1986 as a means to understand users' acceptance of information systems or technologies. TAM offers valuable insights into students' acceptance and utilization of digital libraries, which are technology-driven educational tools. By examining factors like perceived usefulness and ease of use, this theory sheds light on how these aspects can impact students' adoption and utilization of digital library resources for personalized learning (Davis, 1989).

Constructivism emphasizes the active process of knowledge construction by learners as they interact with the learning environment (Devi, 2019). Jean Piaget (1896–1988) is widely recognized as the founding figure of the constructivist perspective on learning. This theory can be utilized to investigate how personalized learning experiences,

facilitated by digital libraries, empower final-year Economics education students to independently build their understanding of economic concepts and theories.

Review of Empirical Studies

Students' Awareness of Digital Libraries in Public Universities in Nigeria

It is vital for students to be aware of and utilize electronic information resources to access necessary information and stay informed. Proficiency in information and communication technologies (ICTs) is crucial for effectively navigating these resources, which are accessible through telecommunication channels (Akpojotor, 2016). A study conducted by Quadri et al. (2014) uncovered a low level of awareness among students in public universities in Ogun State regarding the resources available in digital libraries. The study indicated that many students were unfamiliar with the available resources and struggled to utilize them effectively, likely due to a lack of orientation and training on how to make use of digital library resources.

Similarly, Yebowaah and Plockey (2018) conducted a study that also highlighted a low level of awareness among students regarding the resources available in digital libraries. The study indicated that students were unaware of various digital library resources such as e-books, e-journals, and databases. This lack of awareness can be attributed to insufficient promotion and marketing of the digital library resources. Furthermore, in their study, Okiki and Ireko (2022) examined the extent of awareness and usage of digital educational databases among final year students in private universities located in southwest Nigeria. The results indicated that the final year students displayed a high level of awareness and utilization of digital educational databases. The primary reasons cited by these students for using digital educational databases included completing assignments, academic purposes/coursework, consulting reference sources, accessing research materials, and preparing seminar presentations and project materials. The study also revealed a significant correlation between demographic factors, access to resources, and the utilization of digital databases among final-year students. Based on these findings, the study recommended that libraries acquire more digital educational databases instead of print versions. Furthermore, libraries should enhance their awareness and orientation campaigns to familiarize students with digital educational databases.

Students' Usage of Digital Libraries in Public Universities in Nigeria

Several research studies have examined the utilization of digital libraries by students in public universities in Nigeria. These empirical investigations have delved into different facets of digital library usage, such as the types of resources accessed, the frequency of usage, and the challenges encountered by students. The findings from these studies consistently indicate a limited level of awareness and utilization of digital libraries among students. The underlying causes for this situation can be attributed to various factors, including insufficient infrastructure, inadequate funding, inadequate training for both students and staff, and a lack of policies that encourage the utilization of digital libraries (Akpojotor, 2016; Okiki & Ireko 2022; Bana et al., 2019).

In a study conducted by Daramola (2016), the perceptions of undergraduate students at the Federal University of Technology, Akure regarding the use of e-resources in the library were examined. The study findings indicated the primary motivations for utilizing

e-resources were for assignments and research purposes. Among the e-resources, e-journals, e-books, and e-magazines were most commonly accessed by the students. While the students held positive perceptions of the e-resources, the most significant challenge they faced was a lack of sufficient computers in the e-library. Based on the study's findings, it was recommended that efforts be made to encourage female students to utilize e-resources similar to their male counterparts. Furthermore, an increase in the number of computers in the library was suggested to meet the students' needs effectively.

According to a study conducted by Bana et al (2019), students predominantly utilized digital libraries for research-related objectives, with a particular focus on accessing academic journals and e-books. Nearly half of the undergraduate students surveyed rated their proficiency in using e-resources as high. The study's findings emphasized the significance of carefully selecting and offering appropriate e-resources and services to cater to students' needs across various subject areas within the university. Additionally, another study highlighted those postgraduate students demonstrated higher usage of e-resources compared to their undergraduate counterparts. It was observed that access to reliable internet played a crucial role in influencing the level of e-resource utilization among students (Edem & Egbe, 2016).

A more recent study by Popoola and Adedokun (2023) revealed a significant relationship among the use of electronic library resources by the respondents and computer self-efficacy, computer anxiety and cognitive skills. Computer self-efficacy, computer anxiety, and cognitive skills individually and jointly had a significant influence on the use of electronic library resources of the respondents. The study therefore recommended that, library management in the tertiary institution should give due consideration to computer self-efficacy, computer anxiety, and cognitive skills of the respondents when planning to enhance their use of electronic library resources among others.

Overall, these studies suggest that while digital libraries are becoming increasingly important for students in Nigerian public universities, there are still significant challenges that need to be addressed in order to ensure that all students can access and use these resources effectively.

Challenges Faced by Students in Accessing and Navigating Digital Library Tools

Challenges faced by students in using digital libraries include poor internet connectivity, inadequate training on how to use digital library resources effectively, and limited access to up-to-date resources (Igbo et al., 2022). However, another study found that students who received training on how to use digital library resources were more likely to use them effectively (Bana et al., 2019). Afolabi and Uhomoibi (2017) identified various challenges faced by students, including financial constraints, cultural factors, and issues related to data management and record-keeping. The study proposed the development and implementation of diverse business models to address the needs of the education sector effectively. Additionally, it emphasized the importance of recognizing established practices in traditional education systems, which may require revisions to accommodate changes associated with e-learning. These revisions, however, are not overly complex and can be adequately considered and accommodated. The study emphasized the need to maintain accreditation and standards for learning outcomes, regardless of the variations in delivery methods. E-learning was found to streamline the curriculum and

enhance the reputation of educational institutions. To fully realize the potential of e-learning, it is crucial to make appropriate investments at the right level and at the appropriate time.

Recognizing the Significance of Digital Libraries and Personalized Learning Experiences for Students

Understanding the significance of digital libraries and personalized learning experiences for students is of utmost importance. Scholars such as Arapi (2016), Ajuwon and Oshiname (2018), Adakawa and Musa (2021), and Egielewa et al. (2022) have emphasized the multitude of benefits associated with these educational resources. Digital libraries provide flexible learning opportunities that allow students to participate from any location, while their accessibility on various search engines ensures ease of use. The learner-centered approach of digital libraries enables students to progress at their own pace, and the availability of online resources 24/7 ensures uninterrupted access to information. Moreover, Tsybulsky (2020) observed that digital libraries offer cost-effective solutions by providing a wealth of resources at a fraction of the cost of traditional learning materials. Additionally, collaborative learning is facilitated through these platforms, allowing participants to interact and engage with one another. The availability of multimedia content and simulations further enhances the learning experience, and the scalability of digital libraries allows content to be accessed by audiences of any size. Overall, recognizing and harnessing the potential of digital libraries and personalized learning experiences can greatly benefit students and transform the educational landscape.

In a subsequent investigation, Afolabi and Uhomoibi (2017) discovered that 72% of British students utilizing digital libraries demonstrated a higher level of ease in comprehension, whereas only 58% of Nigerian students experienced the same level of ease. Several authors have conducted research on students' perception of digital libraries as active participants. However, according to Linjawi and Alfadda (2018), prior knowledge of information and communication technologies (ICT) and access to a reliable internet connection contribute to an enhanced personal learning experience for users of digital libraries. Furthermore, Afolabi and Uhomoibhi (2017) proposed that challenges faced by institutions include a lack of electricity, insufficient bandwidth, and connectivity issues.

Summary of Literature Review

The study draws from the Technology Acceptance Model to explore the acceptance of digital library resources and employs the Constructivism Theory to understand personalized learning experiences. It investigates students' awareness of digital libraries in Nigerian public universities, their usage patterns, challenges encountered in accessing and navigating these resources, and highlights the importance of digital libraries and personalized learning experiences for students.

This research bridges a gap in the literature by examining the relationship between digital library tools' acceptance and personalized learning experiences among final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. While previous studies have explored digital libraries and learning experiences individually, this study uniquely combines these elements to provide a comprehensive understanding of how digital library tools impact personalized learning in a specific academic context.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

For this study, a descriptive survey design was utilized. The selection of this particular design was deemed suitable as it allows the researcher to effectively depict the characteristics of the participants without introducing any interference or manipulation to the variables.

Population and Sample

The target population used in the study consisted of all the final year Economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The population consisted of 268 students selected from three public universities in Lagos State who offer Economics Education – Lagos State University of Education (LASUED), Lagos State University (LASU) and University of Lagos (UNILAG) (145 students from LASUED, 60 students from LASU, and 63 students from UNILAG). The sample for the study consisted of 212 students calculated using Slovin's formula (106 students from LASUED, 52 students from LASU, and 54 students from UNILAG). The sampled students were selected using snow ball sampling technique.

Data instruments

Primary data was obtained through the use of a self-constructed questionnaire titled – “Digital Library and Personalized Learning Experiences of Students Questionnaire”. The questionnaire consisted of 31 items, spread within five sections. Section one consisted of the demographic data of the students such as gender and institution; Section two consisted of 13 items on level of awareness of digital library resources, section three, 1 item on usage, measured on scale of six frequencies, section four, 12 items on personalised learning experiences and section five, 5 items on challenges faced by student. The questionnaire was validated using content and face validity type and subjected to reliability test using Split-Half coefficient.

Table 1. Reliability statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	.863
		No of Items	16 ^a
	Part 2	Value	.831
		No of Items	15 ^b
Total No of Items			31
Correlation Between Forms			.554
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		.713
	Unequal Length		.714
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			.708

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The reliability statistics gave an alpha value of 0.86 and 0.83 for the first and second half of the instrument respectively. This result showed that the instrument is reliable (Morgan et al, 2019).

Procedure

The instruments were administered to the 212 sampled students of public universities in Lagos state using google forms, sent through the head of class in each of the three universities sampled. However, only 201 forms were retrieved and all found to be valid.

Data Analysis

The collected data underwent analysis employing descriptive statistics, which were utilized to present the demographic information through frequency counts and percentages. Additionally, mean, and standard deviation were employed to address the research questions. Inferential statistics used is simple linear regression to test hypotheses 1 and 2 at a significance level of 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic Data of the Respondents

Table 2 showed the frequency distribution of the demographic variables of final year Economics education in Lagos State public universities. It revealed more female, 137(68.2%) to male, 64(31.8%) students. The result agrees with Daramola (2016) who found more female than male students in Federal University of Technology, Akure. The table also revealed that 52 (25.9%) are LASU students, 99 (49.3%) are LASUED students and the remaining 50 (24.9%) are UNILAG students.

Table 2. Distribution of final year economics education students

Demographic Variable		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	64	31.8
	Female	137	68.2
	Total	201	100
Institution	LASU	52	25.9
	LASUED	99	49.3
	UNILAG	50	24.9
	Total	201	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Level of Awareness the Resources in the Digital Library

Research Question One: What is the level of awareness of final year Economics education students of the resources in the digital library in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 3. Students' level of awareness of the digital library resource

Items	VA	A	NA	Mean	SD	Decision
JSTOR	99 (49.3%)	63 (31.3%)	39 (19.4%)	1.70	.775	Not Aware
Google Scholar	38 (18.9%)	103 (51.2%)	60 (29.9%)	2.11	.691	Aware
Project MUSE	78 (38.8%)	83 (41.3%)	40 (19.9%)	1.81	.744	Not Aware
Sciencedirect	74 (36.8%)	81 (40.3%)	46 (22.9%)	1.86	.762	Not Aware
ProQuest	75 (37.3%)	84 (41.8%)	42 (20.9%)	1.84	.747	Not Aware
Springer Link	97 (48.3%)	74 (36.8%)	30 (14.9%)	1.67	.723	Not Aware

Items	VA	A	NA	Mean	SD	Decision
Oxford Academic	41 (20.4%)	81 (40.3%)	79 (39.3%)	2.19	.751	Aware
Willy Online Library	73 (36.3%)	90 (44.8%)	38 (18.9%)	1.83	.724	Not Aware
EBSCOhost	114 (56.7%)	63 (31.3%)	24 (11.9%)	1.55	.699	Not Aware
ACM Digital Library	84 (41.8%)	84 (41.8%)	33 (16.4%)	1.75	.721	Not Aware
Research4life	60 (29.9%)	78 (38.8%)	63 (31.3%)	2.01	.784	Aware
Heinonline	109 (54.2%)	64 (31.8%)	28 (13.9%)	1.60	.722	Not Aware
LexisNexis	109 (54.2%)	65 (32.3%)	27 (13.4%)	1.59	.716	Not Aware

Criterion Mean = 2.00; Weighted Mean = 1.81; Std. Dev = .74; Overall Decision = Not Aware
Key: VA = (Very Aware); A = (Aware); NA = (Not Aware); SD = Standard Deviation, Mean
Threshold: If the mean is 0.000-1.999 = Not Aware; 2.000-2.499 = Aware; 2.500-3.000 = Very Aware

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 3 showed that final year Economics education students are “Not Aware” of the resources in digital libraries in public universities in Lagos State Nigeria, as revealed by the weighted mean of 1.81 and Std Dev = .74. Out of the 13 digital library resources listed, students seem to be “Aware” of only three resources which are “Google Scholar”, “Oxford Academic” and “Research4life”. This result negates the findings of Okiki and Ireko (2022), which revealed that the final year students displayed a high level of awareness of digital educational databases in their school libraries.

Frequency of Usage of the Resources in the Digital Library for Research Purposes

Research Question Two: What is the frequency of usage of the resources in the digital library for research purposes by final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Table 4. Students' Frequency of Usage of the Digital Library Resources

How often do you make use of the Digital Library Resources?					
Items	Frequency	Mean	Std. Dev.	C. Mean	Decision
Daily	25 (12.4%)	3.93	1.583	3.5	Good
Weekly	11 (5.5%)				
Monthly	41 (20.4%)				
Once per semester	34 (16.9%)				
Once per session	56 (27.9%)				
Not applicable	34 (16.9%)				

Key: Std. Dev. = (Standard Deviation); C. Mean = (Criterion Mean)

Mean Threshold: If the mean is 0.000-1.499 = Not Applicable (Very Poor); 1.500-2.499 = Once per session (Poor); 2.500-3.499 = Once per semester (Fair); 3.500 to 4.499 = Monthly (Good); 4.500 to 5.499 Weekly (Very Good); 5.500 – 6.000 Daily (Excellent)

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 4 showed that final year Economics education students make use of the digital library resources “Monthly” which is “Good” as shown by weighted mean of 3.93 and Std.

Dev of 1.58. About 167 out of 201 sampled students which represent 83.1%, make use of digital library resources while the remaining 16.9% of them do not make use of the library. The outcomes of this result are similar to the submission of Bana et al. (2019), whose research work observed high proficiency in the use of e-resources in the library on nearly half of the undergraduate students surveyed.

Challenges Faced Students Accessing and Navigating Digital Library Tools

Research Question Three: Are there any challenges faced by final year economics education students of public universities in Lagos State in accessing and navigating digital library tools?

Table 5. Challenges faced by final year economics education students in accessing and navigating digital library tools

Items	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
Lack of training or support on how to effectively use the digital library	4 (2.0%)	36 (17.9%)	90 (44.8%)	71 (35.3%)	3.13	.773	Agree
Difficulty finding relevant resources	5 (2.5%)	49 (24.4%)	100 (49.8%)	47 (23.4%)	2.94	.759	Agree
Difficulty navigating the library's interface	6 (3.0%)	36 (17.9%)	95 (47.3%)	64 (31.8%)	3.08	.783	Agree
Slow loading times of the digital tools in the library	9 (4.5%)	39 (19.4%)	95 (47.3%)	58 (28.9%)	3.00	.815	Agree
Limited access to certain digital resources	4 (2.0%)	38 (18.9%)	85 (42.3%)	74 (36.8%)	3.14	.788	Agree

Criterion Mean = 2.50; Weighted Mean = 3.06; Std. Dev = .78; Overall Decision = Agree
Key: SD = Strongly Disagree; D = Disagree; A = Agree; SA = Strongly Agree; Std. Dev. = (Standard Deviation)
Mean Threshold: If the mean is 0.000-1.499 = Strongly Disagree; 1.500-2.499 = Disagree; 2.500-3.499 = Agree; 3.500 to 4.000 = Strongly Agree;

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Table 5 showed that students face challenges in accessing and navigating digital library tools, which ranges from lack of support on the use of library tools to limited access to some digital resources as revealed by weighted mean 3.06 and Std. Dev 0.78. This is in consonance with the findings of Igbo et al. (2022) where it was revealed that challenges faced by students in using digital libraries include poor internet connectivity, inadequate training on how to use digital library resources effectively, and limited access to up-to-date resources.

Digital Libraries Influence on Personalised Learning Experiences

H₀₁: Digital libraries do not have any significant influence on personalised learning experiences of final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State

Table 6. Simple linear regression analysis coefficients digital libraries influence on personalised learning experiences

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
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	β	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	30.494	1.25		27.101	.000
Frequency of use of the Digital Library Resources	2.002	.266	471	7.536	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Personalised Learning Experiences

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The findings from *Table 6* illustrate the outcome of regression analysis conducted on final year Economics education students. It examined the influence of the frequency of using digital library resources on personalized learning experiences. The results indicated that the intercept coefficient (β_0) is 30.494, accompanied by a standard error of 1.25, a t-statistic of 27.101, and a p-value of 0.000. Similarly, the slope coefficient (β_1), representing the impact of the frequency of digital library resource usage on personalized learning experiences, is 2.002, with a standard error of 0.266, a t-statistic of 7.536, and a p-value of 0.000. It is worth noting that the slope coefficient (β_1) is positive, suggesting a positive influence of digital library resource usage frequency on personalized learning experiences. Consequently, the hypothesis is rejected. This result agrees with the submission of Tsybulsky (2020) that the availability of multimedia content and simulations enhances the learning experience, and the scalability of digital libraries allows content to be accessed by audiences of any size.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the influence of educational tools in digital libraries on the personalized learning experiences of final year economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The findings herein empower lecturers to enhance economics education through digital libraries, elevating teaching quality by integrating tools, fostering self-directed learning, critical thinking, and research skills, and enriching the educational experience with dynamic learning environments and diverse assessment techniques. For economics education students, leveraging digital libraries enhances learning, deepens understanding, hones digital literacy, offers autonomy in pace, and empowers advocacy for improved access and integration, shaping education positively. It was concluded from the study that there are more female to male students in public universities in Lagos State. It also showed that final year Economics education students are "Not Aware" of the resources in digital libraries in public universities in Lagos State Nigeria. Out of the 13 digital library resources listed, students seem to be "Aware" of only three resources which are "Google Scholar", "Oxford Academic" and "Research4life". Furthermore, the study showed that final year Economics education students make use of the digital library resources "Monthly" which is "Good". About 167 out of 201 sampled students which represent 83.1%, make use of digital library resources while the remaining 16.9% of them do not make use of the library. While students are also found to be facing some challenges in accessing and navigating digital library tools, which ranges from lack of support on the use of library tools to limited access to some digital resources. Finally, the study concluded that there is a positive influence of digital library resource usage frequency on personalized learning experiences of final year Economics education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were considered imperative; Public universities in Lagos State should take steps to raise awareness among final year Economics education students about the available resources in digital libraries. This can be achieved through targeted communication campaigns, workshops, and orientation sessions. Efforts should be made to expand the range of digital library resources available to students. While three resources were found to be well-known among students, it is crucial to diversify and provide access to a wider array of educational tools and databases relevant to their field of study. Recognizing that students face challenges in accessing and navigating digital library tools, universities should offer comprehensive support and training programs. This can include workshops, online tutorials, and assistance from librarians or technical staff to ensure students are well-equipped to utilize the available resources effectively. Regular assessment of students' usage patterns, feedback, and challenges related to digital library resources is crucial. Public universities should establish mechanisms to collect and analyse this data to identify areas for improvement, refine strategies, and ensure the evolving needs of students are met effectively.

REFERENCES

- Adakawa, M. I., & Musa, A. U. (2021). Adoption and Use of E-learning in Nigerian Higher Institutions for Sustainable Socio- Economic Development. *Proceedings of the Ahmadu Bello University Library Complex International Conference*.
- Afolabi, O. O., & Uhomoibhi, J. (2017). E-learning implementation in higher education: aspects of infrastructure development challenges and students learning approaches. Available at: <https://pure.ulster.ac.uk/en/publications/e-learning-implementation-in-highereducation-aspects-of-infrastru-3>
- Ajuwon, G. A., & Oshiname, R. M. (2018). Use of Library Resources by Undergraduate Students from Two Tertiary Institutions in South West, Nigeria. *University of Ibadan Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1(1), 1-15.
- Akpojotor, L. O. (2016). Awareness and usage of electronic information resources among postgraduate students of library and information science in Southern Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 1408. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1408>
- Arapi, P. (2016). Toward Pedagogy-Driven Personalized Learning Experiences in Cultural Digital Libraries. *Serdica Journal of Computing*, 10(2), 167p-196p.
- Bana, D., Eze, M. E., & Esievo, L. O. (2019). A comparative study of the use of electronic resources by LIS and computer science students in two Nigerian universities. *Library Hi Tech News*, 36(9), 6-10.
- Daramola, C. F. (2016). Perception and utilization of electronic resources by undergraduate students: The case of the Federal University of Technology Library, Akure. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4(5), 366-370.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Technology acceptance model: TAM. Al-Suqri, MN, Al-Aufi, AS: Information Seeking Behavior and Technology Adoption, 205–219.
- Devi, K. S. (2019). Constructivist approach to learning based on the concepts of Jean Piaget and lev Vygotsky. The NCERT and No Matter May Be Reproduced in Any Form without the Prior Permission of the NCERT, 44(4), 5–19.
- Edem, N. B., & Egbe, N. (2016). Availability and utilization of electronic resources by postgraduate students in a Nigerian University Library: A case study of University of Calabar, Nigeria. In *Information and Knowledge Management* 6(2), 60-69.

- Egielewa, P., Idogho, P. O., Iyalomhe, F. O., & Cirella, G. T. (2022). COVID-19 and digitized education: Analysis of online learning in Nigerian higher education. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 19(1), 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20427530211022808>
- Igbo, H.U., Ibegbulam, I.J., Asogwa, B.E., & Imo, N.T. (2022). Provision of digital information resources in Nigerian university libraries. *Information Research*, 27(3), paper 936. Retrieved from <http://InformationR.net/ir/27-3/paper936.html> (Archived by the Internet Archive at <https://bit.ly/3eu2rL1>) <https://doi.org/10.47989/irpaper936>
- Linjawi, A. I., & Alfadda, L. S. (2018). Students' perception, attitudes, and readiness toward online learning in dental education in Saudi Arabia: a cohort study. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*. 9(1) 855–863.
- Morgan, G. A., Barrett, K. C., Leech, N. L., & Gloeckner, G. W. (2019). *IBM SPSS for introductory statistics: Use and interpretation*. Routledge.
- Niqresh, M. (2019). Digital Library and Intellectual Issues--Issues in Copyright and Intellectual Property. *International Education Studies*, 12(1), 114-127.
- Okiki, O. C., & Ireko, B. Z. (2022). Awareness and use of digital educational databases by final year students in selected private universities in southwest Nigeria. *Nigerian Online Journal of Educational Sciences and Technology*, 4(1), 131-142.
- Olajide, O., & Adio, G. (2017). Effective utilisation of university library resources by undergraduate students: A case study of Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and practice*. Gale Academic OneFile, link.gale.com/apps/doc/A500261784/AONE?u=anon~83e7c2cd&sid=googleScholar&xid=25f4efc4. Accessed 18 July 2023.
- Popoola, S. O., & Adedokun, O. O. (2023). Computer self-efficacy, computer anxiety, cognitive skills, and use of electronic library resources by social science undergraduates in a tertiary university in Nigeria. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 55(1), 111-122.
- Quadri, G. O., Adetimirin, A. E., & Idowu, O. A. (2014). A study of availability and utilization of library electronic resources by undergraduate students in private universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and information science*, 6(3), 28-34.
- Stolyarov, Y.N. (2021). Digital library studies: The subject and definition. *Scientific and Technical Libraries*. 7(1), 14-32.
- Tsybulsky, D. (2020). Digital curation for promoting personalized learning: A study of secondary-school science students' learning experiences. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 52(3), 429-440.
- Yebowaah, F. A., & Plockey, F. D. D. (2018). Awareness and use of electronic resources in university libraries: A case study of University for Development Studies Library. *Library Philosophy and Practice (ejournal)*. 1562. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1562>